

Local Government in Albania

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Structure of Local Government

4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Albania: An Introduction

Elton Stafa, *NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South-East Europe*

Since assuming power in 2013, the new socialist-led Government of Albania initiated a comprehensive decentralization reform process composed of three key pillars: (i) territorial and administrative reform aiming at the re-organization of the first-tier local government units in Albania to create larger and stronger local governments ; (ii) political decentralization reform by consolidating and expanding local governments rights and responsibilities through a new Law on Local Self-Government; and (iii) fiscal decentralization reform through the adoption for the first time of a comprehensive Law on Local Self-Government Finance.

In 2014, the Government of Albania, adopted a Territorial and Administrative Reform (TAR), consolidating the very fragmented 308 rural communes and 63 urban municipalities into just 61 larger municipalities.²³ In practical terms, communes were amalgamated to the ‘closest’ or ‘historical’ urban center and are now called ‘administrative units’. The second tier of local governments was not affected by the territorial and administrative reform.

This TAR constitutes a major milestone in the country’s effort to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of public administration and the quality of public services. The reduction in the number of local government units should increase the efficiency of local government by lowering administrative costs. The concentration of human and financial resources in a smaller number of larger local government units should increase the effectiveness of public services by enhancing the ability of local governments to respond to the preferences of their electorates. And the transfer of additional responsibilities for delivering day-to-day public services to larger local government units should allow the national government to focus more of its energies on the strategic, legislative, and policy-making functions of the state—including the goal of balanced territorial development.²⁴

As a result of the TAR, the average size of the first-tier local self-government units in terms of population increased by 5.4 times, from 8,700 inhabitants to over 47,000 inhabitants. However, despite the territorial consolidation, there is still a large variation in the size of local self-governments among the new municipalities in terms of population, from 3 200 inhabitants for the smallest and youngest Municipality of Pustec to the capital of Tirana, which had over 760,000 inhabitants in 2017, according to the civil register data. The Municipality of Tirana, being the largest one in terms of population, urbanization and economic development, is

²³ Law no 115/2014 on the Administrative-Territorial Division of Local Government Units in the Republic of Albania.

²⁴ Tony Levitas and Elton Stafa, ‘Creating an Equitable, Transparent, and Predictable Unconditional Grant Formula’ (USAID’s Planning and Local Governance Project PLGP 2015) <https://www.plgp.al/wp-content/uploads/2.-Unconditional-Grant-Policy-Paper-September-30-2015-Clean_eng-2.pdf> accessed 18 May 2019.

subdivided into 24 administrative units, eleven subdivisions of the former municipality and 13 communes that merged after the reform. In terms of territory, after the TAR, on average, the size of the first-tier local self-government units increased by 69 times, with a maximum of 479 times in the case of the Municipality of Skrapar. The territory of the new Municipality of Tirana grew by 28 times. The government declared that the main rationale behind the amalgamation was the territorial continuation and historical, cultural, traditional and economic elements. However, the opposition has raised concerns that the new administrative division was based much more on political rather than objective variables. As a result, the opposition did not participate in the design of the new administrative division of Albania, and the reform was approved with the votes of the ruling coalition only. From this perspective, the territorial division may be revised with the change of government in Albania, and in fact in January 2020, as part of the electoral reform, the opposition called for the revision of the territorial and administrative division. While the Constitution allows for a change of the territorial and administrative division through a law that takes into account history, culture and tradition, recent reforms have been in practice top-down processes driven by the central government.

The Constitution grants to local governments the right to amalgamate and create joint institutions and establish forms of inter-municipal cooperation. Between 2000 and 2014, however, there has been only one case of voluntary amalgamation of two communes in the north of Albania. This indicates perhaps a lack of incentives from national and local policymakers to promote and engage in voluntary amalgamations, as it would result in either loss of power or risk of loss of power with implications on local and national politics. Similarly, a severe inheritance from the past in terms of close 'government' presence at territorial level and lack of trust in institutions may have prevented citizens to engage in an active manner to support amalgamations. By the same token there have been only few isolated cases of inter-municipal cooperation, although allowed by the legal framework and desirable in terms of economic efficiency, in particular in the case of smaller municipalities. Conversely, with the new territorial and administrative division, there have also been cases where newly established municipalities preferred to create their own municipal structures to perform certain functions instead of continuing with the joint management of previously existing utilities that was serving multiple jurisdictions.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Legal Documents:

Law no 115/2014 on the Administrative-Territorial Division of Local Government Units in the Republic of Albania

Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications:

Levitas T and Stafa E, 'Creating an Equitable, Transparent, and Predictable Unconditional Grant Formula' (USAID's Planning and Local Governance Project PLGP 2015)

<https://www.plgp.al/wp-content/uploads/2.-Unconditional-Grant-Policy-Paper-September-30-2015-Clean_eng-2.pdf>

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